

INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL SILENCE WITH ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF IRAN KARATE FEDERATION EMPLOYEE'S PERFORMANCE

Negar Hoseini¹ⁱ,

Korosh Veisi²

¹Department of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Kurdistan Science and Research branch,
Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran

²Department of Physical Education and Sports Sciences,
Sanandaj branch, Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran

Abstract:

The present study's aim was investigating the relationship between organizational silences with Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance. The research method strategically was: descriptive, in terms of field study. The statistic society consisted 300s of federation leaders, assistants, chiefs and secretaries of karate associations, referee's committee leaders and also financial and accounting officers. Sampling method was simple random method, 168 were selected via Morgan Table. The measuring tool in this research was Hersey and Goldsmith standard questionnaire of organizational silence and job performance. The questionnaire's date to test the hypothesis of Pearson correlation coefficient, and t test one sample and regression in SPSS software was used. Finding results showed that there isn't a significant relation between organizational silence and employee's performance. Due to the research results and considering more than average organizational silence between the employees, some strategies should be considered at Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation to decrease organizational silence.

Keywords: organizational silence, job performance, karate federation

ⁱ Correspondence: email koroshveisi@yahoo.com

1. Introduction

One of the ways to secure the organizations superior performance should be followed in successful human resources management role playing. To attain the organization's purpose we should sport from client affairs personal. The managers in relation to various issues try on going control of their staffs. They imagine that when a person is hired, he (she) should accept all the organization conditions. Some directors insist on employee's satisfaction through reward and encourage. They may imagine that their employees are their subordinates and they should accept orders. Although the employees are under high financial pressure, they intend and consider economical subjects, but gradually they are interested in meaningful works and willing more job independence to feel self- worthy in the case the directors give their staff's cold shoulder they occur job frustration and withdrawal in their organization that ends to "organizational silence" phenomena.

Pinder & Harlos (2001) described organizational silence "staffs and employee's" prevention of behavioral, cognitive and effective assessments about the organization conditions. Morrison & Milliken (2000) declared that silence has been changed to a powerful force in the organizations, but serious researches and studies have not implemented about it. They introduced this concept and showed that organizational silence is a social phenomenon that is created in an organizational level and is influenced by so many organizational characteristics. These characteristics consist: decision making, management, culture and employee's conception and understanding the effective factors on silence behavior. In experts idea, organizational silence by preventing negative feedback, excludes effective organizational changes and promotion (of course the organizations using method of management style types is an important factor to create or destroy silence climate. A manager that looks his employees as subordinators who have not the right of decision making or announce their comments and as the ones that only their duty is performing orders cannot expect anything except silence. (Zarei Matin et al, 2012). There are different attitudes about circumstances of job performance.

In experts idea, in terms of individual, performance is the individual's success history (Golafshani, 2011). It refers to performing duties. In the other side each organization within its duties and tasks acts (the duties that the organization is established for them). Obviously the individual's duty is a part of the organization and he is obliged morally or legally to do his duties. Performance is the way of doing his activities, so performance (or action process) consists: a collection of the individual's

behavior in relation with their job show. In other words, performance is calculating and measuring the results (Khoshbavar Rostami, 2009).

In a study by Enayati & Bozorgnia Hoseini at 2015, between medical sciences employees of Mazandaran, the results showed that there is a negative relation between organizational silence and job performance; it means that by increasing silence, employee's job performance decreases and vice versa.

The results of Sadeghi studies at 2014 showed that there is a negative and inversely significant relation between organizational silence and employee's performance. Between top managers (directors) and supervisors attitude about silence with employee's performance the relationship is negative and meaningful (significant). Between existing communication opportunities and employee's performance, there is a positive and significant relation.

More communication opportunities in the organization means less silence for employees and their performance will be more favorable. The results of Matin's researches (2012) showed that between motivation job factors and need for success between Fars province physical education employees there is relation. Given that organizational silence subject is a new and unfamiliar subject in scientific and organizational societies of subject in scientific and organizational societies of Iran and less literatures and studies can be found in this relation, in addition silence causes lack of idea and decision alternatives analysis that in this case it's less possible to do a general analysis to decision making process. This will end to failure or effectiveness reduction of job success, organizational changing and decision making process (Zarei Matin et al, 2011).

When silence is dominated in the organization, the viewpoints and ideas are not declared. But in addition you should know it may have other consequences and in addition to satisfaction and job success reduction and will have negative effect on the other job performance and organizational variables, that determines the organizations future. This phenomenon is followed by serious consequences at Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation. And also due to studying the research history, no investigating exist related to the relationship of organizational silence with job performance and job success at Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation, therefore identifying factors and reason of organizational silence and its effect on employee's performance and job success is essential to secure continuation of the organization's life.

1.1 Hypothesis

1. There is relation between organizational silence with Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance.

2. The organizational silence between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees is higher than average.
3. The situation of job performance among Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation staffs and employees is higher than average.

2. Organizational silence

Organizational silence is described as: employee's prevention of declaring behavioral, cognitive and effective assessments (Pinder & Herios, 2011). Silence is effected by many organizational characteristics. These characteristics include: decision making process, culture management process and employees perceptions that are effective in silence (Demitris & Vecula, 2007). But at the same time the two basic factors cause employees silence in the organization include:

The managers fear of negative feedbacks from the employees because of their position and interests may be in danger and the employee's imagination about management's beliefs about them. These implicit beliefs include some management thoughts based on the employees only consider their personal interests. The organization's director or manager knows more than the others and knows the bests and that difference in opinion are essentially harmful problems for the organization.

However, these issues are the manager's beliefs and none of them may not be realistic in the organization, but create harmful emotions such as: fear, deception, anger between the organization's members, and finally causes silence between employees (Slad, 2008).

2.1 Organizational silence dimensions

Silence is not always an indicative of a passive behavior, silence can be active, knowingly, intentional, purposeful. This is an important subject because indicates complicated and multi-dimensional nature of silence. In fact some forms of silence are strategic and non-passive, and can be consciously, purposeful, intentional like when the employees prevent to present confidential information, against the other. The silence that is intentional and passive (based on submission and accepting every situation) is different from an intentional but non-passive (Van- Dyne et al, 2003).

Despite that, organizational silence generally is referred to intentionally lack of declaring ideas, information and employee's ideas but based on the intention and motivation of silence in the employees it's different in nature.

In table 1 there are examples of silence types and silence motivations.

Table 1: The staffs or employees silence motivations

Employees motivation type	Employee's silence: intentional prevention of expressing idea, information's and job related opinions.
Isolated behavior: based on submission and un ability to make change	Submissive silence: prevent express ideas because of being surrendered against retaining ideas by themselves and because of less self- efficacy to make changes
Self- conservative behavior: based on fear, anxiety, and being in danger feeling.	Defensive silence: preventing to express information because of problems rooted in fear. Conceal the facts because of self- protection.
Altruism behavior: based on collaboration feeling, humanism and kindness	Altruism silence: prevent to present confidential information because of cooperation, protect proprietary knowledge to benefit the organization

2.2 Job performance

Job performance is as an effective component in the organization that has been an important part of organizational studies (Ezhei et al, 2009). It's a word that covers not only the activity's concept to act and also the works result in the same time (Yamani, 2000: 110). One of the main discussed subjects in organizational issue comes back to the right perception of job performance reasons (Farokhnezhad et al, 2011: 78). The result of past researches showed that team identity has a big share in more assistance to teams and their better performance (Krimer Venvoot, 1999: Krimer & Vendayk, 2002).

2.3 Job performance evaluation

After that, a worker or an employee do a job for a while, his performance is evaluated (Hafman, 2000). Performance evaluation is a process that the director or manager evaluates the employee's work behavior by measuring and comparing pre- arranged standards through it, and records the results and announce the employees.

A performance evaluation system consists on organizational process and operations related to performance evaluation. In performance evaluation, the manager and subordinator are cooperated, whereas performance evaluation system consists organizational policy, activities supporting resources and regulations. Programs and intervals of evaluation, the way of evaluator and evaluable determination, the ways and methods of evaluation records and information delivery and storage the right perception of job performance reason (Farokhnezhad et al, 2011: 78). The result of past researches shows that team identity has a big share in more assistance to teams and their better performance (Krimer Venvoot, 1999: Krimer & Vendayk, 2002).

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Recruitment, training and upgrading, motivation and payment. Performance evaluation exists in all four parts and connects via preparing feedback information from other parts. In fact, performance evaluation is known as one of strong and important tools for human resources management (Greefman, 2007).

3. Research methodology

The present research is strategically descriptive, in terms of implementation is surveying, in terms of aim and purpose is practical and from data collection aspect is a field study. The statistical society consists. 2, 8 members of Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation directors and their assistants, karate association directors, referee committee directors and also finance and accounting officers that in the present time are working. Sampling method in this research is simple random.

To determine the sample volume Morgan table is utilized and considering that the statistical society is obvious, 168 individuals were selected. As statistical sample measuring tool in this research are Vacula and Buradus (2005) organizational silence questionnaire and Herisi and Goldsmith (1981) job performance questionnaire. The questionnaire of organizational silence created by Vacula & Buradus in 2005 and consisted 3 dimension. Such as: superior management attitude to silence, the administrator's attitude to silence and relationship opportunities. Validity of the questionnaire was admitted by the experts and professors and its reliability in the main study, in 2005, coefficient of reliability calculation (Cronbach's Alfa) related to this

dimension were estimated 89/0. And also the reliability of this questionnaire, at Iran was calculated by Adel Salvati, YahyaYarahmadi and Seyede Nadia Hashemi were calculated 889/0 using Cronbach's Alfa. Job success questionnaire consist 30 questions, was created by Rodsip (1984). Its reliability was determined using Cronbach's Alfa coefficient 79% in inner consistency method, and its formal validity was admitted by 12 professors. Job performance Hersey & Goldsmith questionnaire in 1981 was designated and credited by Hersey & Goldsmith. In a research in 2009 by Sara Sadat Ardestani, Mandana Momeni PhD and Amir Babak Marjan, PhD, in this research to determine questionnaire's reliability, 79 people were selected as sample, and the questionnaire was available for them and then Cronbach's Alfa method was utilized. Cronbach's Alfa rate in performance variable was obtained (863/0). All variables and the entire questionnaire consist more than 7/0 Alfa.

For data analysis, coefficient correlation Pearson regression test and also one sample t test in SPSS software used.

4. Results

4.1 First hypothesis

There is relation between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance and organizational silence.

There is no relationship between organizational silences with Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

There is relationship between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

Due to the following table results if the significant level value is more to than error value, we conclude zero (0) hypothesis, and if the significant level value is smaller than error value, we conclude hypothesis (1).

Table 2: The result of Pearson correlation coefficient test between organizational silences with Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance

	Employee's performance	
Organizational silence	Pearson correlation	-093/0
	Sig	228/0
	N	168
P<0/05		

Considering the above table, because the significant level is larger than 05/0 and the result is that, the hypothesis (the research hypothesis) based on existing relationship

between organizational silences with Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance is rejected. In this part the hypothesis inferential analysis, using single group t test and with theoretical mean (average) 3 for 1st and 2nd hypothesis and theoretical average 2 for 3rd hypothesis, is presented.

Second hypothesis

The situation of organizational silence in between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's is higher than average.

Table 5: The results of single sample t test about 2nd hypothesis

Index Hypothesis	Number	Average	Standard deviation	Test value= 3		
				sig	df	T
3rd hypothesis	168	09/3	41/0	003/0	167	99/2

The above table data shows that because $t = 99/2$ value in significant level $\alpha = 0/05$ is significant and meaningful, and because experimental level is larger than theatrical level, so it's concluded that totally organizational silence is higher than average among between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

Third hypothesis

The situation of job performance is higher than average among between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

Table 6: The results of single T test about 3rd hypothesis

Index Hypothesis	Number	Average	Standard deviation	Test value= 3		
				sig	df	T
4th hypothesis	168	57/2	53/0	001/0	167	-29/10

The table data shows that, because $t = -29/10$ in significant level $\alpha = 0/05$ is significant and because experimental average is smaller than theoretical average, so its concluded that generally Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performance isn't higher than average.

Third hypothesis: The situation of job success among Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation is higher than average.

5. Discussion and conclusion

A. First hypothesis

There is relation between organizational silence and Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

The results of Pearson coefficient correlation in this hypothesis, in significant level 05/0, showed that there isn't a significant relation between organizational silence Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employee's performances. It means that by investigating correlation between job performance dimensions with organizational silence, the relationship between employee's job performance and organizational silence is not significant.

In explaining obtained finding it can be said that by considering organizational silence is a psychological and internal matter in an organization, it isn't so much related to employee's job performance. In addition, you should know that, the organizational silence may have other consequences, and beside satisfaction and job commitment reduction, using negative affect on other job and organizational variables they that endorse on organization's destiny. May be one of the main damages due to it can be considered lack of employee's sodality with organizational changes. So it's concluded that one of very important duties of the organization's directors and managers identifying and breaking the organizational silence atmosphere, to secure the organization's life through this way.

This result is only conformed with the results of Enayati and Bozorgnia Hoseini (2015), that showed that there isn't any relation between organizational silence and employee's job performance, it means that by increasing silence, it doesn't influence the employee's performance and vice versa.

B. Third hypothesis

The organizational silence is higher than average between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees.

The results of t test in this hypothesis showed that organizational silence is higher than average between Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation employees. It suggest that the employees don't consider themselves responsible against the organization's affairs, and due to inadvertency or fear of management they keep silence, and the dominant atmosphere to karate federation is in a way that employees can not declare their ideas, suggestions and their requests and they are feared of its consequences.

It can be said that karate federation employees for different reason prevent suggestions about the organization and it increases silence in karate federation. Silence is a very important sign for illness, stress, aging, depression or fear in the organization, and as soon as possible karate federation authorities should follow the factors, and solve them. Inadvertence to this issue can have very bad consequences and even ends to the organization's death. Fear of suggestions, fear of being neglected by senior managers and fear of their ideas using less, keep their ideas without any reward, causes increasing organizational silence at Islamic Republic of Iran karate federation. As you see, the most important reason for organizational silence at karate federation is fear and insecurity feeling.

The results of this hypothesis in this research is adopted with Erchi et al (2010), that showed organizational silence in Turkey organization's is an a high situation, and whereas organizational silence and congestion are somewhat a new phenomenon for Turkish organizations the results of this study were shared, by creating awareness about organizational silence, not only for scientists but also for executive agents at Turkish organizations.

C. Fourth hypothesis

The status of job performance among staff of the Karate Federation of the Islamic Republic of Iran is higher than average.

The results of the single sample t-test in this hypothesis showed that the job performance among employees of the Karate Federation of the Islamic Republic of Iran is not higher than average. This conclusion suggests that the employees of the Karate Federation of the Islamic Republic of Iran have relatively good job performance. Job performance as the expected overall value of each organization is an indicator for determining the level of productivity and productivity, and one of the most important outcomes of the organization's interest. Previous research results show that good job performance has a high contribution to better organization and better performance. By studying the research background, a study that was consistent with the results of this hypothesis was not found.

5.1 Suggestions

According to the results obtained in this study, the organizational silence among Karate Federation employees is higher than the average level. The following suggestions can be made to reduce organizational silence to managers:

- Establishment of human resource management improvement programs to teach decision-making skills and conflict in problems to cope with organizational silence in the Karate Federation.
- Make decisions collectively, and give importance to groups and committees of work at the Karate Federation staff.
- Identification of the capabilities and abilities of employees of the Karate Federation and their use in executive affairs and decision making.
- Identification of the individual and personality characteristics of Karate Federation staff to assign responsibility to them.
- Formulate regulations to support the views of staff at the Karate Federation and encourage staff to provide feedback.
- Develop professional skills of karate federation staff and use the experiences and skills of past faculty members to enhance their career success.

Also according to the results obtained in this study, which showed that job success among Karate Federation employees is not higher than the average level, the following suggestions can be made to increase job success for managers:

- Conducting training courses, lectures, seminars and distributing related publications and brochures, and ... in improving the skills of Federation staff in enhancing job success.
- Facilitates the professional skills of the Karate Federation staff to increase job success.
- Increasing human capital and staffing levels in the Karate Federation, leading to increased earnings and promotion of job prospects and job success.

Also, based on the results obtained in this study, the job performance among staff of the Karate Federation of the Islamic Republic of Iran is not higher than average. You can offer managers the following suggestions to increase job performance:

- Increasing the federal staff salaries and salaries to improve the career performance of Karate Federation staff.
- To motivate employees to increase their innovation and provide new ideas.

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Negar Hoseini, Korosh Veisi
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